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High-throughput screening of SOFC cathode materials

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Abstract

Lanthanum and strontium manganites, cobaltites and ferrites (LSM, LSC and LSF, respectively) have been extensively used as oxygen electrodes in solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) [1]. None of them provide all the requirements for operating by themselves as cathodic material due to issues related with low ionic conductivity, low stability and/or incompatibility with the rest of constitutive SOFC materials. One of the approaches followed to overcome these inconveniences has been the combination among them, aiming to obtain mixed properties. A successful example of this strategy is the LSCF which presents mixed conductivity at intermediate temperature [1] and nowadays is commonly used as cathode in IT-SOFCs. However, when LSCF is employed a protective layer is needed to screen the YSZ electrolyte due to the reactivity between them.

Following this approach, in this work a high-throughput methodology is employed for the preparation of a LSM, LSC and LSF ternary compositional map. Combinatorial Pulsed Laser Deposition is a very efficient procedure that allows the fabrication of multiple samples with different compositions in a single experiment [2]. Previous works showed the benefits of this method applied to a LSM + LSC binary system [3]. In this case in which a ternary system is studied, additional features are expected due to the likely natural trend of different stoichiometric samples to give rise to a variety of structures, properties or even phases.

Initially, the simulation of the deposition process will allow us to determine the best configuration to obtain the largest compositional distribution throughout the wafer area. Besides, prediction of thickness and composition gradient is anticipated. In this initial stage of the work, assessments of phase purity, thin film stability and morphology and, compositional map generation are shown.

Introduction

Since the invention of SOFCs in late 1950s, great efforts have been made in order to overtake every drawback that the technology presents. Among them, those limitations related with the cathode have required intensive energies due to the high Area Specific Resistance (ASR), particularly at intermediate temperature range, in comparison with the resistance showed by anode or electrolyte [4]. In SOFC technology, plenty of materials have been tested as cathodes [5], nevertheless only $\text{La}_{0.8}\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{MnO}_{3+\delta}$ (LSM), $\text{La}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3+\delta}$ (LSCF) and $\text{Sm}_{0.5}\text{Sr}_{0.5}\text{CoO}_{3+\delta}$ (SSC) are employed commercially. Actually, LSM-based electrodes have been preferred among other alternatives since its first application due to the easiness for the fabrication of LSM-YSZ composite electrodes without forming secondary phases even when $\text{La}_{0.8}\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{CoO}_{3+\delta}$ (LSC) and $\text{La}_{0.8}\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{FeO}_{3+\delta}$ (LSF) exhibit much lower polarization losses [6-8]. However, mild temperatures are needed when sintering LSC and LSF together with YSZ due to the risk of secondary phases formation [9,10]. Combination of these two latter lanthanides to generate LSCF has resulted in an improvement of the fuel cell performance with respect to LSM-based SOFCs due to its mixed ionic/electronic conductivity which allows delocalization of TPBs throughout the microstructure [11]. In spite of this fact, LSCF presents long-term stability issues that concern for practical applications. Additionally, like its single parent compounds it has reactivity with YSZ making necessary the use of a buffer layer, mostly based on ceria-related materials, between electrolyte and air electrode [11].

Regarding LSMCF ternary formulations (with general formula $\text{La}_{0.8}\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{Mn}_{1-x-y}\text{Co}_x\text{Fe}_y\text{O}_{3+\delta}$), some groups have already attempted to study their properties within SOFC context [12,13]. However, in these works both groups selected only one composition. It is noteworthy the discussion of Montero *et al.* [13] in which they correlated the elemental composition of different materials to the functional properties shown, even suggesting how increasing the amount of a certain element could improve the performance. Special attention deserves the work presented by Rossini *et al.* [4] which, following a combinatorial dip-printing method for preparing the samples, studied possible relations among composition and crystalline phase or oxygen non-stoichiometry in the LSMCF system.

Furthermore, deposition techniques, such as Pulsed Laser Deposition (PLD), have shown its great potential to develop thin films of functional materials, increasing the power density of SOFCs especially at intermediate temperatures. In particular, PLD thin cathode films have been successfully used to investigate the Oxygen Reduction Reaction (ORR) mechanism and improve cathode performance [14,15].

1. Scientific Approach

Searching for new improvements in SOFC technology, i.e. increase of performance and/or decrease of degradation; here we propose the preparation of novel SOFC cathode formulations by Combinatorial PLD of LSM, LSC and LSF. By this methodology, considered a continuous compositional spread (CCS) technique, a compositional map of the three parent compounds is obtained in one experiment. While the preparation by conventional methods would take a considerable amount of time delaying the progress, our work will take advantage of exceptional properties of PLD in terms of deposition velocity, controlled microstructure and stoichiometry transfer to fabricate a whole set of samples with multiple compositions simultaneously, reducing significantly the time consumed in the preparation. Afterwards, evaluation of physicochemical and electrochemical properties of the generated materials will help to select an optimized composition for the proposed application.

2.1 Experiments

Thin-film growth of the individual materials as well as the ternary compositional map was achieved by pulsed laser deposition with a KrF excimer laser (248 nm wavelength) onto single crystal (100)-oriented Si or single crystal YSZ wafers (YSZ, 6.5 mol% Y₂O₃-stabilized ZrO₂, 3" dia., 500 μm thick.) substrates (UniversityWafer Inc.). For this purpose, commercial targets (SurfaceNet GmbH) of La_{0.8}Sr_{0.2}MnO₃ (LSM), La_{0.8}Sr_{0.2}CoO₃ (LSC) and La_{0.8}Sr_{0.2}FeO₃ (LSF) were employed. The films were deposited at 700°C employing 100mJ under an oxygen backpressure of 20 mTorr. For thin films grown onto silicon wafers, a previous YSZ layer was deposited in order to avoid deleterious interaction of Si and the materials studied. Combinatorial PLD deposition was achieved by rotating the substrate 120° every time that the target changed. The deposition parameters were optimized in order to grow 1 nm of each compound in each cycle, ensuring a good intermixing among the three materials.

After the deposition, dicing of the wafers was attained in order to get chips of 10x10 mm. As-grown films were characterized by grazing incident X-ray diffraction (GIXRD, PANalytical XPERT-PRO, Cu K α source) in $\theta/2\theta$ mode with 0.02° step size. Microstructural and thickness analysis was performed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) in a ZEISS AURIGA microscope. EDS analysis at wafer level was achieved at 14 keV and an acquisition time of 200 s.

For checking the stoichiometric transfer in the ternary sample, microprobe analysis by Wavelength Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (WDS) is planned. However, there was no time for carrying out these analyses by the time of submission of the abstract. In any case, WDS analysis in Co-substituted LSM binary compounds prepared by the same method showed a good correspondence between the targets compositions and the thin film produced by combinatorial PLD method [16].

2.2 Simulations

A Matlab program was developed to simulate the PLD deposition process. Since the deposition area is finite, a model which allows studying the influence of the deposition parameters in the compositional map obtained was considered necessary in order to optimize the distribution of different formulations evaluated.

3. Results

Plume study of the parent compounds

Fig. 1a shows an LSF thin film grown onto a 4" Si wafer. The different concentric colored rings indicate a variation of the film thickness. This is the simplest case. However, since our objective was the study of three compounds, two more plumes will be present in the same wafer. Thus, during the deposition overlapping of the three plumes (each one corresponding to a parent compound) will happen, modifying the compositional range attained based on the relative position among them in a first approximation. Therefore, the determination of the optimum distance among the three plumes has been identified as a critical factor. In this sense, the laser incidence position and the substrate rotation angle are the deposition parameters controlling this factor because they allow governing the plume position and hence the degree of interaction reached. On the other hand, different materials will present specific plume shapes which will equally influence the ternary map generated. Taking into account these facts, a simulation of the deposition process was

developed. This program models the deposition of each plume using a Gaussian distribution function. Reference data for the individual plumes were acquired from the deposition of the respective parent compounds in 4" silicon wafers. Values in two orthogonal directions were taken with the aim of minimizing the error committed when simulating the plumes due to possible asymmetries in the plume shape (see Fig. 1b and Fig. 2a & b below).

Fig. 1 a) LSF thin film grown onto a 4" silicon wafer showing x- and y-directions used for plume shape analysis; b) LSF thickness distribution along the x-axis.

Fig. 2 a) LSM plume thickness distribution along the x-axis; b) LSC plume thickness distribution along the y-axis.

As it can be seen in the figures above a relatively good correspondence between the experimental data and the regression is obtained, supported by a coefficient of determination (r^2) minimum value of 0.99.

After the deposition, some wafers were diced in 10x10mm chips for easiness of characterization. SEM microstructural analysis of materials surface reveals the high density of the films (see Fig. 3), characterized by showing nanometric grain size. Every film fabricated seems to be stable but LSC thin film which shows multiple cracks, indicating

microstructural instability likely due to a greater thermal expansion mismatch [17]. Another interesting feature of the layers fabricated is the columnar microstructure that they present.

Fig. 3 SEM images of the parent compounds thin films (From top to bottom: LSM, LSC and LSF, respectively. Left images: cross-section, right images: surface).

Afterwards, data obtained of the Gaussian regression, in particular the standard deviation for each compound in both directions, were introduced in the program and simulation of the deposition process was attained. Different laser incidence positions were tested in order to find the best compromise between the relative distance of the plumes and the compositional map produced. Bearing in mind that our target is to deposit over 3" diameter YSZ substrates, a distance of ca. 7.8 cm among plume maxima was selected.

Plume study of ternary compositional map

Fig. 4a shows a 3D representation of the plume shape for the three different parent compounds. In this case, a maximum thickness of 180 nm for each compound was chosen. However, looking at the color bar on the right of the graph it can be seen that the maximum thickness is ca. 210 nm. This is due to the overlapping among the plumes. Actually it can be appreciated that the darkest red color, which means the greatest thickness, belongs to LSF plume while the other plumes remain closer to the set value. This fact evidences a greater influence of LSM and LSC over LSF plume; hence, it will not be possible to obtain pure LSF in the combinatorial deposition under these deposition conditions. Similar information can be extracted from Fig. 4b where a 2D contour map corresponding to the former simulated deposition process is shown. In this case, closer isolines indicate larger thickness. In turn, LSF isolines are much closer in comparison with the ones corresponding to LSM and LSC contributions. Additionally in Fig. 4b, two circumferences, black and red, corresponding to the wafer area (i.e. 3" diameter) and the limiting deposition area, respectively, are shown. From here it is shown that under these deposition conditions plume maxima will be out of the wafer. Since our ternary diagram will be made by joining the three plume peaks, which presents the maximum respective composition for each parent compounds, our compositional range will not reach 100% for any of the components.

Fig. 4 a) 3D representation of the plume shape for the three parent compounds; b) Contour map of the thickness evolution for the three parent compounds.

Following the aforementioned approach, a ternary diagram is built where each vertex meet one plume top position (see Fig. 5a). The different molar fractions are determined by the isolines for the respective compounds. Several features associated to the interaction among the individual components are observed in the diagram. First, due to the strong impact of LSC and specially LSM over LSF the triangle appears distorted. Moreover, as it was anticipated the compositional map created does not cover the whole range (0-100%). It is almost fully complete for LSM and LSC but the Gaussian nature of the plume thickness distribution and the particular standard deviation values prevent to obtain pure composition zones within the 3" dia. wafer. Further distances among the individual components must be used to avoid such interaction; however, this will decrease the range of compositions reached. In any case, the properties of the pure compounds are well known and it is not the aim of this study.

Fig. 5 a) Ternary diagram of LSM, LSC and LSF system; b) Combinatorial PLD deposition of LSM, LSC and LSF on a 3" silicon wafer. Note: compositional isolines are not meeting in the triangle edges of a) due to the presence of ternary compounds at these points.

Finally, Fig. 5b shows a silicon wafer where a combinatorial PLD deposition of the three parent compounds LSM, LSC and LSF was made. A stronger interaction of LSM and LSC with LSF evidenced by a darker coloration on the left corner is revealed which is in good accordance with the simulation.

Characterization of ternary combinatorial sample

Fig. 6 shows three different X-ray diffractograms obtained for the same LSMCF combinatorial sample. XRD spectra were collected from the expected region where all the compounds should be present. Diffractograms of pure compounds were added in the graph as well to allow comparison. In any of the cases, no additional peaks apart from the ones visible in the pure compounds patterns were observed. However, the peaks are

Fig. 6 XRD patterns of pure LSM, LSC, LSF and combinatorial LSMCF

attributed to a cubic crystalline structure instead of a rhombohedral/orthorhombic as for LSM, LSC and LSF. In this sense, differences observed in the space group could be due to a lack of resolution when analyzing thin films or a preferential growth orientation as it seems to happen for the planes (100) and (200) of LSMCF with respect to the pure compounds.

Microstructural analysis by SEM was carried out at a central point of the wafer. Fig. 7 shows a dense film with no cracks. The main feature observed in this case is the heterogeneous nanometric grain size of the surface sample at this point, going from ca. 30 nm to more than 100 nm.

Fig. 7 SEM image of combinatorial ternary LSMCF sample.

Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) was used to carry out an initial elemental compositional analysis. Although local, it allows us to get some information regarding the elemental distribution in the ternary sample. In this way, atomic ratios among cations occupying B positions, i.e. $B^i/(B'+B''+B''')$, were calculated. In Fig 8 this evolution is represented all over the wafer area by means of circular sector diagrams allowing us to correlate the position in the wafer with the relative concentration of each metal: Mn, Co and Fe. Clear trends in the elemental composition are evidenced which correspond well with the data anticipated by the simulation.

Fig. 8 Diagram showing the evolution of the composition over the wafer area.

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